

The Synergetic Principles of Sustainability and Co-evolution of Complex Systems

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Abstract: The hope of finding a new outlook on the world, new methods of cognition and prediction of course of historical processes, may be connected with the theory of self-organization of complex systems, called also synergetics, as a new interdisciplinary field of research. Synergetics facilitates our understanding of evolutionary pathways of the complex social and human systems, the causes of evolutionary crises, the threats of catastrophes, the reliability of forecasts and the principle limits of predictability in ecology, sociology, economy, geo-policy.

Synergetics provides us with the knowledge of constructive principles of co-evolution of complex social systems, co-evolution of countries and geopolitical regions being at different stages of development, integration of the East and the West, the North and the South. Due to the growth of population on the Earth in blow-up regime, the general and local instability of development is increasing. The social world seems to go towards a unity, a sustainable commonwealth through a pulsation rather than monotonously. It goes via alternation of disintegration, even if partial, and getting more powerful integration of structures. There is a pathway of multiple reduction of temporal and material expenses, path of a resonant excitation of a desirable and - that is not less important - feasible in a given social system structure. In the case of right topology of integration of geopolitical structures, an arising whole organization can accelerate its tempo of evolution.

Key words: Co-evolution, complex systems, openness, nonlinearity, nonlinear management, self-organization, sustainable development, synergetics.

SYNERGETIC APPROACH TO 'SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT'

The modern notion of 'sustainable development' can be considered quite differently from the synergetic point of view. Synergetics, or the theory of self-organization and evolution of complex systems, is a new interdisciplinary field of research. Our hopes to find a new, non-traditional outlook on the complex evolutionary world may be connected with the theory.

Synergetics is considered here as a new movement in modern science signifying a process of becoming of a new outlook of a human on the world as well as on himself in the world. Synergetics entails a new dialogue of a human with nature, a new synthesis of human knowledge and wisdom. Synergetics is a new approach to cognition of evolutionary crisis, instabilities and chaos, to mastering the methods of nonlinear management of complex systems being in the states of instability.

The theory of self-organization gives us knowledge of constructive principles of sustainable development and co-evolution of complex social systems, co-evolution of countries and regions being at different stages of development. The complex social systems cannot be forced on our free will towards some arbitrary developmental structures. It's necessary to understand how their own trends of development may be facilitated, how we can provide the systems with a self-maintaining, sustainable development.

The general formulation of the principles of sustainability and co-evolution are as follows:

- integration of simple structures into a complex one occurs through their tempos of life, rates of development;

- weak, but topologically rightly organized influences upon a complex system are of great efficiency;
- future states of complex systems are open in form of spectra of predetermined possibilities, structure-attractors;
- there is a possibility - in the case of right, "resonant" topology of integration - of significant economy of material and spiritual expenses and acceleration of tempo of the complex system development etc.

That's why synergetics can become a foundation for making justified decisions and predictions under conditions of uncertainty, stochastic shocks, periodic reorganization of geopolitical structures.

IN THE SEARCHES OF A NEW NONLINEAR EVOLUTIONARY THINKING

It is not justified to use old methods and models in modern time, in conditions of the informative revolution and the wide use of personal computers, taking into account the recent results of mathematical modeling of the complex socionatural processes and computational (by use of computers) experiments. The former methods were based on the patterns of linear thinking, on the linear approximations and extrapolations from available. They were often connected with attempts to construct models of excessive complexity, to include in them more and more parameters of complex social systems.

The former methodological approaches to the complex social systems modeling didn't take into account, or, at least, underestimated, alternatives of future, factors of determination of evolutionary processes from the future, the constructive role of chaotic elements in evolution, the meaning of fast, avalanche-like processes, so called blow-up regimes, in development of complex systems and some other significant peculiarities of the complex evolutionary world.

"Self-organization", "nonlinearity", "openness", "co-evolution", and "chaos" are key words specifying the synergetic investigations. Along with these concepts, synergetics concentrates its attention on the studies in *complexity*. Synergetics is cognition and explanation of something complex, its nature, principles of self-organization and evolution.

Sustainability can be considered in the light of the theory of complexity as well. The *sustainable development* means a self-maintaining development. It is the development being in accordance with inner, own trends of complex systems. Sustainability is closely connected with the ways of self-management and self-control.

Being a modern post-Darwinian paradigm of evolution, the theory of complexity and self-organization is being now under rapid development in different countries by various scientific schools: H.Haken (1978, 1984), I.Prigogine (Prigogine 1980, 1989; Prigogine and Stengers 1984), S.P.Kurdyumov (Achromeeva et al. 1989; Kurdyumov 1990; Samarskii et al. 1995), E.Laszlo (1996), K.Mainzer (1994), B.Mandelbrot (1982), E.Morin (1992), F.Varela (Maturana and Varela 1988), etc.

The paper is based on the generalizing and philosophical comprehension of the recent research results obtained by the Moscow synergetic school at the Keldysh Institute of Applied Mathematics of the Russian Academy of Sciences. Synergetics has a peculiar image here. It is under development as a theory of non-stationary, fast evolving localized structures in dissipative open and nonlinear media (systems), their growth, transformation, synthesis and decay (Achromeeva et al. 1989; Kurdyumov 1990; Samarskii et al. 1995). It is treated here as a theory blow-up regimes.

According to the approach, synergetics makes a close study of the ways of co-evolution (coexistence and joint, mutually correlated development) of complex systems in our

complicated and still disunited world. To put it differently, theory formulates principles of evolutionary holism. Besides, synergetics explores where does history flow on, where do the evolutionary processes follow to, i.e. builds a kind of evolutionary teleology (Knyazeva 1997). A new, based on the synergetic knowledge, worldview and a new methodology of cognition and forecasting of development of complex systems are expounded in our book (Knyazeva and Kurdyumov 1994) as well as in the book of abstracts of the Moscow Forum of Synergetics (Knyazeva 1996).

BRIDGING GAPS BETWEEN THE NATURAL SCIENCES AND THE HUMANITIES

Two main discoveries force us to revise the usual worldview. They constitute a basis of a new theory, the theory of self-organization. These are the discoveries of strange attractors and of blow-up regimes. Both of them are of great philosophical significance. They create a kind of bridge from synergetics, which originated mainly in natural sciences (in nonlinear analysis, non-equilibrium thermodynamics, theory of chaos, fractal geometry), to some research fields in the humanities (to cognitive science, epistemology, sociology, demography, economics) (Knyazeva 1996).

The availability of strange, or chaotic, attractors is one of fundamental facts in the theory of self-organization. The strange attractors have been discovered by now almost everywhere, in various fields of natural and human world, starting with meteorology and ending in neurophysiology, investigation of the human brain activities. Strange attractors show us the limits of predictability of evolutionary processes and the availability of areas of principal unpredictability of some phenomena. This means the understanding of probabilistic, chaotic behavior of dynamic systems which is determined not by limitations of our investigative instruments, but by the very nature of the systems.

Another fundamental fact is the law of population growth. We are used to believe that the processes of rapid growth, such as the population growth, "economic miracle" or information explosion, occur according to an exponential law. As a matter of fact, it is one of the myths of the classical science. Most of the processes of avalanche-like growth occur much more rapidly, in a blow-up regime when some characteristic values increase infinitely during a finite period of time.

The blow up regimes are being studied in plasma physics, meteorology, ecology (the growth and dying out of biological populations), neurophysiology (the modeling of signal propagation along neural nets). There exist similar blow-up regimes in social and cultural development. The growth of information as well as of the population on the Earth obey a law of hyperbolic growth, i.e. the processes occur in blow-up regimes (Kapitza 1996a, 1996b).

Due to interdisciplinary character of the fundamental discoveries, synergetics can lead to a new dialogue between specialists in natural sciences and in the humanities. Synergetics takes some steps towards a synthesis of these two qualitatively different realms of scientific research.

FIELD OF EVOLUTIONARY WAYS INTO THE FUTURE

A whole system of concepts, notions and ideas connected with nonlinearity and "aims" of evolution, i.e. signifying the construction of a kind of evolutionary teleology, is in the process of development now. First of all, these are the notions of localization processes in open dissipative media (structures formation in continuous dissipative systems), spectra of structure-attractors as the most stable formations on which evolutionary processes in such

systems go out, the ways of resonant excitation of evolutionary structure-attractors, types of fast, avalanche-like development, blow-up regimes (modes with peaking) (Achromeeva et al. 1989; Knyazeva and Kurdyumov 1994, 1995; Kurdyumov 1990; Samarskii et al. 1995).

A new notion has appeared: open nonlinear medium (complex system) can be viewed as a carrier of future organization forms. In relatively simple mathematical and computational models a result of fundamental importance has been obtained: a continuous nonlinear medium potentially contains in itself different kinds of localization processes (different kinds of structures). Medium is a united source that acts as a carrier of different forms of future organization and as a field of different evolutionary paths.

Thus, notion of *spectra of evolutionary paths of complex systems*, of fields of developmental paths, constitutes a basis of the synergetic methodology. The notion entails a number of important consequences: the plurality of the future, the availability of the moments of instability connected with the choice of a path of further development, the specific role of a human in the nonlinear situations of branching evolutionary paths and choosing a desirable, favorable path of development.

It's important to understand that social systems usually have several alternative paths of development. There are many developmental paths. They are determined by spectra of structure-attractors of social systems as a kind of complex nonlinear systems. Besides, some eventual changes of social systems can lead to a transformation of spectra of evolutionary structure-attractors, of sets of possible paths into the future.

We have to be aware that different evolutionary trends are available in any complex social system. An exit to the future is not unique. We must take into account multiple futures. But the future states of complex social systems are not simply open and unpredictable: there are certain spectra of possible forms of future organization that are determined by the inner properties of the systems under consideration. Although there can be a lot of evolutionary paths, their number is not infinite. Spectrum of structure-attractors is not continuous. It is not any arbitrary evolutionary path that can be feasible in a given social system.

The future forms of social organization are open in form of a fan of predetermined possibilities. The exits to the future are not unique, but they are narrow. There are certain "corridors" of evolution. Therefore, we have to solve a problem of a controlled openness of the social development: how we can facilitate sustainable and self-maintaining ways of development? How is it possible to choose a harmonic developmental path into the future?

SYNERGETIC RULES OF NONLINEAR MANAGEMENT

The theory of evolution and self-organization reveals some principles of *nonlinear management* of complex systems. The theory teaches us the art of soft management.

1) The future is open and unpredictable, but not arbitrary. There are spectra of possible future states, certain discrete sets of structure-attractors of complex evolutionary processes.

Initial conditions do not determine the vector of human activity; the initial conditions will be forgotten when one of structure-attractors has been initiated. The latent and revealed attitudes determine the present activities. The present state of affairs is constructed by and from the future.

The soft lines of the future presuppose ways of special, soft management.

2) *Soft management* is management by "clever" and appropriate influences. Weak, but proper, i.e. resonant, efforts are of great efficiency. They have to go in line with the inner trends of development of a complex behavioral system.

Correct resonant actions can lead to revelation of tremendous inner forces and possibilities of a human being or a human community. Thus, synergetics rediscovers the well-known philosophical principle: small events cause large results.

3) Some human actions are doomed to be unsuccessful. They fail because they were not in step with the inner trends of the complex system development. There are *evolutionary prohibition rules* (Knyazeva and Haken, 1997) which are imposed on some kind of human actions.

4) There must be a certain *topology of action*. It turns out that the managing influence must not be energetic, but rightly topological organized. Its topological configuration, symmetric "architecture" is important, not the intensity of the influence. Weak, but rightly topologically organized, - resonant - perturbations upon complicated systems are extremely effective.

The *resonant action* is a spatially distributed action. It's a kind of prick in the right places and at the right time.

Synergetics defines how it is possible to multiply reduce time and required efforts, to generate - by the resonant influence - a desirable and, what is no less important, feasible complex structures. This synergetic feature of complex organizations had been guessed thousands years ago by the father of Taoism Lao-Tsu. It was expressed as the weak defeats the strong, the soft defeats the hard, the low defeats the loud.

CONSTRUCTIVE PRINCIPLES OF THE COMPLEX SYSTEMS CO-EVOLUTION

The rationality and even necessity of integration of different cultural, social and geopolitical structures are rather obvious in modern time. Though the process of such integration presents a general trend of development of our civilization, it occurs actually with enormous losses, historical deviations and delays. It turns out that there are some ways of common life, co-evolution, convergence of heterogeneous elements of the world with simultaneous conservation of cultural and historical peculiarities, the quality of life, etc.

Synergetics allows to reveal laws of co-evolution of complex structures "of different ages", i.e. structures being at different stages of evolution and having different rates (tempos) of evolution, as well as laws of "including", building a simple structure into a more complex one (Knyazeva and Kurdyumov 1994; Kurdyumov 1990). The knowledge of the synergetic evolutionary laws opens a possibility to understand ways of integration of countries, regions, geopolitical structures evolving with different speed and being at different stage of evolution.

There are various, but not arbitrary, ways of integration of simple structures into the complex ones. There is a restricted set of integration ways, ways of construction of a complex evolutionary whole.

A certain degree of overlapping of simple structures is very important when a process of integration takes place. There must be a certain topology, "architecture" of overlapping. There must be a positive "feeling of measure".

Market in general sense of the word, i.e. some analogy to chaos, fluctuations, dissipation, is a factor of integration of relatively simple structures into more complex ones. Chaos, so to say various kinds of the exchange processes, plays a constructive role in the moments of choosing a further evolutionary pathway as well as in constructing a complex evolutionary whole. Figuratively speaking, chaos serves as a "glue" which binds parts into a united whole.

Thus, new principles of nonlinear superposition describe how a complex evolutionary whole is being assembled from the integrated parts. Integration of structures is not merely their putting together: the regions of localization of structures are overlapping with energy

defect taking place. In this case, a whole is not equal to the sum of its parts. Generally speaking, it is neither more nor less than the sum of parts. It is qualitatively different. It is an evolutionary whole, because it unites structures of "different ages", the structures being at different stages of evolution.

Synergetics formulates some rules of integrating structures evolving with different speeds into a whole structure. The integration occurs according to their "architecture", topology of organization, the speed of the development. The main principle of integration of parts into a complex whole can be formulated as follows: *synthesis of relatively simple evolving structures into a more complex one occurs due to the establishment of a common tempo of their evolution.*

The intensity of processes in various fragments of complex structure (for example, for social systems - the level of economic development, quality of life etc. in various countries) can be diverse. The fact of integration signifies that structures becoming parts of a whole acquire a common tempo of social development. Structures "fall into one tempo-world", they begin to develop with the same speed. One can speak about the co-existence of "differently aged" structures in the same tempo-world.

Moreover, in the case of right topology of integration (in the case of a certain degree of interaction of structures and a certain symmetry of architecture of a building unified structure), an arising whole organization can accelerate its tempo of evolution.

What is a path to unity? According to the theory of self-organization, any open systems with strong nonlinearity are very likely to pulsate. They are subjected to natural oscillations of development: the differentiation of parts is replaced by their integration, the running apart – by the drawing together, the slackening of ties - by their strengthening. The world seems to go towards a unity through a certain pulsation rather than monotonously. It goes via alternation of the disintegration, even if partial, and getting more powerful unifications of structures.

Aside from a hope that the disintegration of a complex system does not exclude a possibility of its integration in the future, the synergetic worldview offers something more constructive.

First of all, we can reach desired structure-attractors in a shorter time, avoiding numerous absurd and unnecessary attempts, infernos, evils. This is an idea of speeding up the evolution by means of the resonant influence.

Second, considering the prospects of integration, synergetics argues that there are laws for the architecturally perfect unification of differently aged structures (i.e. the structures being at the different evolutionary stages) into a harmonic whole. There is an optimum of the integration, a certain measure of connection of parts within the framework of the whole.

Thus, basing on the understanding of mechanisms of switching over the opposite complementary regimes, the regimes of disintegration and integration, we may assume that a renewal of broken ties will occur using some former, already existed channels. "The spread over the old traces" will appear to take place.

At the initial stage of formation of a complex structure, it is very important whether a topologically proper organization is achieved. When structures of different ages are being integrated into a complex structure, we observe, according to the laws of nonlinear synthesis, a defect of power (or a defect of energy). That is we can save energy and other expenditures. The initial stage of integration would seem to slacken the processes running in an open nonlinear system.

To put it in other words, the topologically proper organization of structures in a whole leads to an approaching of a peaking (blow-up) point. A new higher rate of development is setting up throughout a whole united domain. The whole develops faster than its integral

parts. It becomes more profitable to develop together, because it allows saving the material (in particular, energetic), spiritual and other resources.

Every new way of a topologically right integration of structures, i.e. an appearance of every next layer (with bigger exponent of nonlinearity) of hierarchical organization, accelerates tempo of development of a whole as well as of its integral parts.

Concerning problems under discussion, we may draw a conclusion that a unified, rightly organized market accelerates development of the participating sovereign states. Therefore, a path of formation of a new federation in Russia, and in a general case, a path of growing integration of the sovereign states into the world commonwealth, is to a certain extent predetermined.

SYNERGETICS AS AN OPTIMISTIC PHILOSOPHY

To summarize, new elements of worldview, methodology, futures studies, communicative and educational activities derived from synergetics could be formulated as follows.

First. Some steps were made towards an understanding of synthetic role of the theory of self-organization and philosophy of self-organization, their role in development of dialogue between different scientific disciplines, worldviews and ways of life. Synergetics may be used as a basis for *interdisciplinary synthesis of knowledge*, for open and constructive dialogue between specialists in natural sciences and in the humanities. The theory may facilitate the creation of cross-disciplinary communication. It leads to a new dialogue and synthesis of science and art, science and religion, the West and the East (the Western and the Eastern worldviews).

Second. The hope of finding some new fresh ideas in the investigation of history as well as in the construction of images of future of mankind on the Earth could be connected with the modern developments in the field of synergetics.

Synergetics develops a new evolutionary holism, i.e. explains how a complex evolutionary whole can be assembled from different parts. It gives us knowledge of constructive principles of co-evolution and sustainability of the complex social systems, co-evolution of countries and regions being at different stages of development.

Synergetics builds a new evolutionary teleology. It makes an attempt to construct images of future, spectra of possible forms of future organization. That's why synergetics can become a foundation for making justified decisions and predictions under current conditions of uncertainty, stochastic shocks, periodic reorganization of geopolitical structures.

From the synergetic standpoint, some general views of principles of nature and mankind co-evolution as well as of laws of co-evolution, common life, integration of sovereign states and geopolitical regions into world community, unification of the East and the West, the North and the South, can be developed. One can hope for establishing new principles to unify human personalities and cultural historical communities, to organize a proper space of communication, constructive dialogue between people, bearers of different styles of thinking, cultural traditions and life values.

Synergetics reveals *evolutionary laws of nonlinear synthesis*:

- 1) availability of various, but not arbitrary, ways of integration of structures into a whole complex one,
- 2) importance of a right topology, "configuration" of integration of simple structures into complex ones,
- 3) integration of structures as different tempo-worlds,

- 4) possibility - in the case of right, "resonant" topology of integration - of significant economy of material and spiritual expenses and acceleration of tempo of the system development.

Third. Being interdisciplinary one by its character, synergetics allows to develop some new approaches to education and teaching as well as to effective providing various strata of population with information. The question is of education through the computer programs and diskettes containing new synergetic worldview and new nonlinear ways of thinking, knowledge as know how, synthesizing the modern developments of natural sciences and the humanities. Due to it, the study in natural sciences is becoming more humanitarian, while the humanitarian study turns to be impossible without new natural scientific, nonlinear mathematical methods of research. *New informative technologies* appears to be necessary in the process of education.

Forth. The methodology of nonlinear synthesis based on scientific principles of sustainable development and co-evolution of complex structures of the world can be used as a foundation for modern *world futures studies*, for projecting various paths of mankind into the future.

Generally speaking, synergetics is closely connected with optimism. That is an optimistic attempt to understand the principles of evolution and co-evolution of the complex systems, to reveal causes of evolutionary crisis, instability and chaos, to realize the limits of control and interference in the social systems development and to master the methods of nonlinear management of complex systems. This is an attempt to find ways of facilitating of self-maintaining and sustainable development of the world.

From the synergetic point of view, future is open and varied. There is a spectrum of possibilities of future development. Future is not *'l'avenir'* (what will be tomorrow), but *'les futuribles'* (one of the possible future states). Spectrum of possibilities of future development is not continuous. It is not an arbitrary developmental path that can be chosen by a given complex social system. Future is open in form of a spectrum of predetermined possibilities, in form of an 'evolutionary tree'.

This field of possibilities can transform, reconstruct itself, if the inner properties of the social system are changing. If we manage to model the spectra of developmental structure-attractors of complex social systems, we can get an opportunity to avoid the critical states and undesirable developmental paths and to choose the most favorable, acceptable for us - and at the same time feasible in a given system - path of development. This demonstrates the special role and responsibility of a human subject in the nonlinear situations of bifurcation and choice.

Thanks to synergetics we are finding a philosophy of hope.

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